

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ARCHAIC WORDS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Annotation

This article is dedicated to comparative analysis of archaic words in English and Uzbek

The aim of the article is to study the national-cultural comparative analysis of archaic words of English and Uzbek languages by comparing and learning and knowing the main and crucial differences between each other.

Keywords: archaic, linguacultural, comparative, national, crucial, specificity, reality, phenomena.

Language is considered to be a dynamic process, not a steady phenomenon. As the time passes by, the word stock, that is, the vocabulary of any language modifies by being supplemented with new words and expressions appearing simultaneously with the alterations of the culture, social life of people, development of science, national identities and people's mentality. A certain part of the outdated words in the language usually drops out of the vocabulary of the language completely or remain as elements performing purely historical descriptive functions. As an example, the word "aboard" was used for expressing the meaning of "out of doors", but overtime this word changed into preposition, which expresses to be on a ship, plane or train, moreover, out of the country. This list can be continued to purblind (short-sighted), lurdan (an idle or incompetent person), coz (cousin), afeard/afeared (frightened) and others. the genres of folklore can be main preservative such archaic words, consisting of proverbs, riddles, fairy tales and epics. Therefore, we can see that the combination of peremiologic peculiarities such as the origin, etymological, semasiologically sides of proverbs throughout the article. Valida Madiyorova gave her ideas "Any attempt to describe the present state of proverb scholarship and its desiderata for the nature must by necessity look back upon past accomplishments". Archaic words have attracted the attention of scientists throughout the world. In particular, M. Ondar [1] analyzes outdated words in the texts of Tuvan heroic tales and divided archaic words into the following thematic groups: words referring to the character's title or status; names of

military weapons and attributes of the hero; words referring to household items; and names of human body parts. Karagulova [2] identified a set of archaisms, acquired new terminological meanings, which will serve as a material for collecting glossaries in law and medicine, as well as a linguistic means for professionals of law and medicine. Dobrovolska [3] presents the results of a study of functional, semantic and chronological issues concerning Middle English occupational terms with Scandinavian word stems. N. Turniyazov and A. Rahimov [4], M. Hamroyev et.al. [5], Ulmas Sharipova and Ibrohim Yuldashev [6] paid their main attention to the problem archaic words in their works. But they have opened their ways to explaining and giving examples of the term archaism, as well as to distinguishing it from historical ones. Coming to the definition of an archaic words, they are the use of a form of speech or writing that is no longer current. Another term which can be mixed with an archaism is historism. Historisms are also named obsolete words in English. Their appearance is extra linguistic because of some reasons. According to Merriam Webster "It is the denotatum that is outdated." They are very numerous as names for social relations and institutions and objects of material culture of the past. The names of ancient weapons, types of boats, types of carriages, instruments belong to historisms: battle axe, battering ram. In proverbs' content, we come across a great number of historisms. Such as, "anvil", which is a heavy usually steel-faced iron block on which metal is shaped (as by hand hammering), the original background of this word dates back to Middle English anfil, from Old English; akin to Old High German anafalz anvil; akin to Latin pellere, meaning to beat. We can give as an example the proverb "The church is an anvil which has worn out many hammers" historism which is used in the proverb, express a stylistic meaning. Archaisms have differences from historisms because they are obsolete names for existing objects. Archaisms always have particular feature like they can be easily replaced with their synonyms such as to deem – to think, glee – joy. Great number of proverbs contain archaisms in their content, which we aim to discuss in this work. If we pay attention to the specific features of archaic words in English proverbs, we should mention a scientific research conducted by some scholars, they have analyzed more than 600 proverbs, and found out ninety archaic units used in the context, let's analyze one of them: "As good be an addled egg as an idle bird" Conducting the morphological analysis of the word "addled", it is the 2nd verb form of "addle", that means to confuse someone so they cannot think properly. From the etymological point of view, it has come from Middle English Adel – (in adel eye "putrid egg"), attributive use of Old

English Adela is "filth, filthy or foul-smelling place," going back to Germanic Adela, adel ōn. However, in proverbs, this word expresses an archaic meaning to become rotten, (for eggs producing no chick): As good be an addled egg as adle bird. The core meaning of this is perfectly appropriate to: "A person who is inactive or does not work is as much useless as a rotten egg".

Or another explanation, addled egg expresses an egg that is no longer good to eat or spoiled, and idle bird lays no eggs. So the result is the same, to have a rotten egg equal to have no eggs, we suppose that it can be applied to any useless item that we have. The context that gives closer meaning, also has an archaic word "so'fi"

Amali yo'q so'fidan, tuxumi yo'q tovuq yaxshi.

Echki yugurib lang bo'lmas.

The archaic word "lang" means "Lame", that is a person who unable to walk without difficulty as the result of an injury or illness affecting the leg or foot. Such examples are very common. The modern version is "cho'loq", we know that Amir Temur is also called "Temur Lang". Here the proverb means that the person who works will never be harmed to look backwards for the use of proverbs, we must not forget to investigate their traditional and innovative use in our own time. Proverbs, those old means of generationally-tested wisdom, help us in our everyday life and communication to cope with the complexities of the modern human condition. Let's look through next proverb containing the archaic word "beget":

Length begets loathing. The word "beget" literarily mean to bring (a child) into existence, or form, create, develop, cause bring about, give rise to and others. Here, the word comes to identify to cause, by saying "if the close people will not see each other for a long time or will not talk or communicate for a lengthy period, this affect their relationship". Another definition is given in the book "The facts on file dictionary of proverbs" (2007) by Martin Manser, as follows: "Nobody likes a long-winded speaker or a writer". In both explanations, the archaic meaning of this word defines to cause and to bring about. This archaic word also used in the following form: Love begets love.

In two versions, the archaic meaning of the word beget retains its archaic concept. Another proverb containing archaic word "clout": Never cast a clout, till May be out A clout is an old word for a piece of clothing. According to some individuals "May" refers to the month but others consider that, it means the flower or hawthorn. The tree flowers in late April or early May. In other words, if we see it as an old saying, "Don't take your warm clothes off until the May

blossom is out because cold weather can return during the spring months which is what is happening at the moment”. If we pay attention first at the 'cast a clout' part. The word “clout”, although archaic, is straightforward. Since at least the early 15th century “clout” has been used variously to mean “a blow to the head”, “a clod of earth or (clotted) cream” or “a fragment of cloth, or clothing”. It is the last of these all meanings that is meant in “cast a clout”. We can see its various spelled versions as clowt, clowte, cloot, clute. So, “never cast a clout...” simply means “never discard your [warm winter] clothing...”. The “till May be out” part is where the doubt lies. At a glance, this means “until the month of May is ended”

References:

1. M.V. Ondar, Archaic words in Tuvan heroic legends. The New Research of Tuva. 2020, № 1. URL: <https://nit.tuva.asia/nit/article/view/909>. DOI: 10.25178/nit.2020.1.9
2. B. Karagulova, A. Kushkimbayeva, Sh. Kurmanbayeva, A. Alimkhan, Zh. Kaiyrbaeva, Linguocultural description and formation of archaic words, Indian Journal of Science and Technology, Vol 9(14), DOI: 10.17485/ijst/2016/v9i14/91080, April 2016
3. O. Dobrovolska. Middle English occupational terms with Scandinavian word stems: Functional, semantic and chronological issues, Topics in Linguistics, 2020, 21(2), pp. 80-108
4. N. Turniyazov and A. Rahimov, Uzbek language, Samarkand, 2006
5. M. Hamroyev, D. Muhamedova, D. Shodmonqulova, X. G'ulomova, Sh. Yuldosheva, Mother tongue, Tashkent, 2007
6. U. Sharipova, I. Yuldashev, Basics of linguistics, Tashkent, 2006
7. Madiyorova Valida Quvondiq qizi, A comparative- typological classification of archaic words in English and Uzbek languages, International Journal on Integrated Education, Volume 4, Issue I, January 2021, p.139

